

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Agronomic evaluation of some leading cultivars for the Turkish rice breeding program

Nazimi Açıkgöz, Faculty of Agriculture, Ege University, Bornova, Izmir, Turkey

The evaluation of the world's leading rice material — the first and most important step in rice improvement — not only facilitates selection of the most suitable parents, but also enhances their cultivation.

Agronomic characters of the material listed in the table, evaluated for 3 years, indicate that:

- Cultivars of Italian origin (grown widely in Turkey) did not perform as well as U.S. and Russian cultivars. But U.S. varieties needed a longer vegetative period and Russian varieties had smaller kernels.
- Despite its shorter culms and higher tiller number, the indica group was unsuitable because of other problems. The same was true for indica-japonica hybrids.
- No superior agronomic characteristics

Performance (3-yr av) at Izmir, Turkey, of 18 rice varieties and lines of different origins.

Variety	Grain yield (g/plant)	Panicles (no./plant)	Grains (no./plant)	T.K.W. ^a (g)	Maturity ^b (days)	Plant ht (cm)
<i>IRRI</i>						
IR747B2	12.6	16.2	53.1	18.54	110	62
IR1561-228-3	11.2	13.8	59.1	17.96	133	64
IR2037-625	14.0	12.6	83.1	16.86	123	59
IR2307-64	23.1	14.5	94.3	20.81	119	65
IR2307-117	12.7	14.4	71.5	15.27	128	62
<i>TURKEY</i>						
Dawn (USA)	13.8	5.7	124.4	21.81	120	100
Tongil (Korean)	12.0	8.2	78.2	26.12	116	56
Sarıkilçik	11.1	12.0	34.8	32.62	77	81
Akçeltik	10.9	10.5	41.1	27.96	83	96
Sarıçeltik	14.4	10.1	56.2	27.01	97	109
<i>USSR</i>						
Kuban	16.1	9.6	87.5	26.31	82	91
Krasnodorky 424	14.4	7.6	114.3	27.32	83	100
<i>ITALY</i>						
Ribe	13.1	6.2	71.4	29.62	88	85
Baldo	14.0	7.0	71.3	34.71	84	82
Rocca	12.5	7.9	64.8	30.95	88	83
<i>USA</i>						
Caloro	13.5	6.3	112.6	24.58	122	104
CS-S4	15.8	7.5	108.7	23.76	122	103
Calrose	27.2	11.1	129.5	24.02	122	104
LSD 5%	3.00	2.29	10.95	0.90	—	3.28

^aThousand kernel wt. ^bDays from seeding to harvest.

were observed among the local varieties, except for the shorter

vegetative period in the cultivar Sarıkilçik. ■

Breeding behavior of a cross between two lowland varieties

S. K. Bardhan Roy, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

Pankaj (P₁) and O.C. 1393 (P₂) were crossed at Chinsurah in 1976 kharif in a program to develop intermediate height, high yielding genotypes suitable for the lowlands where water level fluctuates (10–15 cm) depending on rainfall.

O.C. 1393 is a strongly photoperiod-sensitive local variety adapted to the lowlands, and Pankaj (a selection of IR5), is the only high yielding variety widely cultivated in the lowlands during kharif in West Bengal.

F₁ seeds from the cross were grown in the field in 1977 kharif. Photoperiod

sensitivity is considered an essential trait for varieties grown during this season. Therefore, F₂ populations were sown in January and grown during 1978 boro to separate early, long-duration, and photoperiod sensitive segregates. More than 60% of the plants flowered by May; the remaining plants flowered at the end of October or in November and, at 22°52'N latitude, were assumed to be photoperiod responsive. O.C. 1393 flowered only in November 1978 whereas Pankaj flowered irregularly.

Seeds from the individual photoperiod sensitive plants (F₃) and the two parents were grown in lowland plots at IRRI during the 1979 dry season.

Seedling heights at 21 days after seeding (DS) averaged 41.7 cm for O.C. 1393, 30.9 cm for Pankaj, and

39.5 cm for the F₃ population with a range of 30–52 cm. The F₃ population consisted of intermediate or semitall types with an inclination toward O.C. 1393, the taller parent. A transgressive segregation toward the taller types, shown by the range, may be due to a gene for tallness in Pankaj, which is lacking in O.C. 1393. When the two varieties are crossed, the combination of genes produces plants taller than O.C. 1393.

The frequency distribution of F₃ seedling heights showed a normal curve (see figure). This character appears to be polygenic in nature and wide segregates in the F₃ population indicate a possibility of producing intermediate plants from the population.

At 31 DS the F₃ population and the

Frequency distribution of the F_3 population of the cross between Pankaj (P_1) and O.C. 1393 (P_2) among seedling heights.

parents were submerged in water maintained between 45 and 50 cm. After 12 days, 67.4% of the O.C. 1393, 34.1% of the progeny lines, and 27.0% of the Pankaj plants survived.

The increase in height (i.e. elongation ability) of the survivors averaged 66.2 cm for the F_3 lines, 73.2 cm for O.C. 1393, and 45.5 cm for Pankaj.

Thus, Pankaj as a parent in a lowland crossing program may produce desired intermediate plant height with good tolerance for submergence. ■

Contribution of tillers produced at different weeks to panicle formation

Abdur Rashid Gomosta and Md. Zahurul Haque, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca

The potential contribution to panicle formation of tillers produced in different weeks was investigated during the wet season. The short-duration variety Chandina and the medium-duration variety IR8 were grown in pots to avoid mutual shading.

Seedlings of both varieties started

Productive tillers and other yield components of Chandina and IR8 (av of 10 replications).

Variety	Tillers	Productive tiller (%)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets (no./panicle)	Wt/panicle (g)	100-grain wt (g)	Contribution to total panicle wt (%)
Chandina	Primary	100	22	133	1.70	2.19	6
	2d wk	100	21	114	1.50	2.18	12
	3d wk	94	22	117	1.40	2.18	42
	4th wk	13	20	81	0.90	2.10	31
	5th wk	34	18	64	0.70	1.88	8
IR8	Primary	100	23	124	2.00	2.37	10
	2d wk	85	23	114	2.00	2.36	18
	3d wk	93	22	100	1.60	2.28	37
	4th wk	70	21	85	1.30	2.32	30
	5th wk	15	18	57	0.60	1.80	3

producing tillers the second week after sowing. The tillers produced each week until the 7th week after sowing were marked with wire rings.

In both varieties tillers produced within the third week were 93 to 100% productive and those produced in the fourth week 70 to 73% productive. Tillers produced in the 5th week were only 15% (IR8) and 34% (Chandina) productive (see table). None of the tillers produced during the 6th and 7th week developed panicles.

The panicle length, number of spikelets per panicle, and weight per

panicle were the highest in the primary panicle and decreased in subsequent panicles. However, the highest contribution to the total panicle weight was from panicles produced by the 3d- and 4th-week tillers. The 100-grain weight did not vary much among the panicles; however, it was extremely low in the panicles from 5th-week tillers.

A rice plant, whether of short or medium duration, has the potential to produce panicles from 5th-week tillers during the wet season. Such panicles contribute little, however, to the total panicle weight of a plant. ■

Tillering pattern of dwarf indica rice and its contribution to grain yield

R. A. Raju and S. C. Varma, Department of Agronomy, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi — 221005, India

The growth and development of tillers — the prime units of grain production — directly affect the economic and total biological yields. Because basic research on tillering patterns is meager, the present study was undertaken on Cauvery cultivar, an early maturing semidwarf indica rice.

Primary tillers flowered earliest, followed by secondary and tertiary tillers

(see table). Growth parameters, such as plant height and number of rachillae per panicle, were higher in primary tillers. Leaf emergence was rapid and relative growth rate high in the mother culm and primary tillers. Early tillers originating at the same time had better vascular connections with the mother shoot. The diameter of internodes in tertiary tillers that emerged early was nearly double that of later internodes. Because of a large source for carbon assimilation (green leaves) and more sink capacity for accumulating photosynthates (panicles), the primary tillers contributed nearly half of the

Growth parameters and tillering pattern of Cauvery, a semidwarf indica rice, Varanasi, India.

Designation of tiller	Flowering days (no.) from germination	Ht (cm)	Bearing tillers (%)	Rachillae (no./pmick)	Yield contribution (%)
Mother culm	74	102.1	100	115.0	10
Primary bearing	76	99.3	95	103.2	50
Secondary bearing	77	94.5	71	101.7	35
Tertiary bearing	80	93.2	48	98.3	5